

References

1. J. D. HOOKER, "The Flora of British India", L. Reeve and Co., London, Vol. I, p. 41.
2. S. K. TALAPATRA, S. K. ΜΥΚΗΟΡΑΔΗΥΑΥ and B. TALAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 790.
3. H. KAITAWA, T. KUSUMI, H. Y. HSU and Y. P. CHEN, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1970, **43**, 3631.
4. W. E. HILLIS and A. CARLE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, **16**, 147.
5. P. ΜΥΚΗΟΡΑΔΗΥΑΥ, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Calcutta, 1981.
6. A. PELTFF, R. S. WARD, E. VENKATA RAO and K. V. SASTRY, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, **32**, 2783.
7. R. S. THAKUR, M. P. JAIN, L. HRUBAN and F. SANTAVY, *Planta Med.*, 1975, **28**, 172.

Chemical Investigations of the Leaves of *Sida rhombifolia* Linn.

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SIDA rhombifolia Linn. has been used in the indigenous system of medicine under the name *Mahabala* for promoting vigour¹ and in urinary and uterine discharges². We have studied the chemical composition of the leaves of this plant. Fifteen free amino acids, six fatty acids and the total sterolic content of the leaves have been isolated and estimated. Antibacterial activity of the mixture of the fatty acids has also been studied.

Experimental

Isolation and estimation of free amino acids : The concentrated 70% ethanolic extract of the defatted leaves was decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal. The light brown coloured filtrate was then desalted using ion exchange columns³ packed with Amberlite IR 120 (H) and Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The water eluate containing non-ionic constituents gave positive test with Molisch reagent.

Concentrated 5% ammoniacal eluate containing amino acids was spotted on a circular paper chromatogram (Whatman No. 1) and the chromatograms were separately resolved using butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) and phenol : water (5 : 1). Individual amino acids were identified by R_f values, ninhydrin (0.25% in acetone) colours and co-chromatography with authentic amino acid samples. They were estimated colorimetrically by dissolving each coloured spot in 5.0 ml of 75% ethanol and the optical density measured at 540 nm. The quantities were obtained by interpolation of standard curves. Nine amino acids were identified in the butanol system and six in phenol system. Percentage of individual amino acid in the leaves was lysine 1.7, histidine 1.5, arginine 3.5, asparagine 9.8, glutamine 7.4, alanine 0.98, valine 1.5, phenyl alanine 6.1, leucine 1.7, aspartic acid 0.25, glutamic acid 0.25, glycine 0.31, serine 0.32, threonine 0.38 and tyrosine 0.62.

Isolation and antibacterial activity of fatty acids : The petroleum ether (60-80°) extracted material of the air dried leaves was subjected to alkaline hydrolysis⁴ and the unsaponified material was extracted with solvent ether. The saponified material containing fatty acids was acidified with sulphuric acid and extracted with benzene. The concentrated benzene extracted material was esterified⁴ and extracted with hexane to get the methyl esters of the fatty acids. The glc of the mixed esters showed six different peaks which were identified as those of myristic, palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids and an unidentified acid.

The antibacterial activity of the mixture of fatty acids was tested using cup-plate method⁵. The mixed fatty acids showed high antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (inhibition 44 mm) and fairly good activity against *E. coli* (inhibition 26 mm).

Isolation and estimation of sterol : The total phytosterol content in the unsaponified fraction was estimated by colorimetric method described by Zlatkis, Zak and Boyle⁶. The colour of the reaction was measured at 625 nm and compared with that of cholesterol taken as standard. Total phytosterol content in the leaves was found to be 0.052% in terms of cholesterol.

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References

1. K. M. NADKARNI, "Indian Materia Medica", Popular Prakashan, Bombay, 1976, Vol. 1 p. 1197.
2. WILLIAM DAYMOK *et al.*, "Pharmacographia Indica", Education Society's Press, Bombay, 1889, p. 206.
3. E. LEDERER and M. LEDERER, "Chromatography", Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1957, 127.
4. EGON STRAT, "Thin Layer Chromatography", George Allen and Unwin Ltd., London, 1969, p. 371, 372.
5. S. P. HIREMATH, M. G. PUROHIT and M. SIRSI, *Karnataka Univ. J. of Sci.*, (India), 1974, **19**, 208.
6. HEROLD VARIKY, "Practical Clinical Biochemistry", The English Language Book Society, London, 1969, p. 313.

Gravimetric Determination of Copper(II) Using N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2,6-dimethyl)phenylbenzamidinium Hydrochloride

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NUMEROUS complexing reagents such as potassium thiocyanate¹, α -benzoinoxime^{2,3}, salicylaldoxime^{4,5} and rubeanic acid^{6,7} have been suggested for the gravimetric determination of copper(II).